

QUALITY OF HUMAN RESOURCE SERVICES IN OUTPATIENT CARE ON OUTPATIENT SATISFACTION IN HOSPITALS (SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received May 21, 2024 Revised Jun 10, 2024 Accepted Jun 17, 2024</p> <p>Keywords: Quality of Service, Quality of Human Resources, Patient Satisfaction</p>	<p>This study aims to assess the relationship between the quality of outpatient human resource (HR) services and outpatient satisfaction in hospitals through a systematic literature review method. The quality of health HR services is an important factor that affects patient satisfaction, which can ultimately affect loyalty and recommendations from patients. In this review, we analysed various studies published in a given period that evaluated the quality of HR services in outpatient care and their impact on patient satisfaction. Using systematic literature review (SLR) research on research published in high-reputation journals, using PRISMA diagrams for the research method. The results of the literature review show that aspects such as speed of service, competence of medical staff, availability of facilities, and effective communication between service providers and patients are the main factors contributing to patient satisfaction. In addition, the study found that improvements in the quality of outpatient HR services were significantly correlated with higher levels of patient satisfaction. This study concludes that hospitals need to focus on improving the quality of outpatient HR services through staff training, facility improvement, and service management system improvement to achieve optimal patient satisfaction. These findings provide insights for hospital managers and policymakers in formulating strategies to improve service quality and patient satisfaction.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">This is an open-access article under the CC-BY 4.0 license.</p>

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INTRODUCTION

A hospital is a health service facility that provides individual health services in a complete manner through promotive, preventive, curative, rehabilitative, and/or palliative health services by providing inpatient, outpatient, and emergency services (House of Representatives of the Republic of Indonesia, 2023). Outpatient services

include the process of consultation, diagnosis, treatment, and treatment carried out in the clinic or hospital outpatient unit. The quality of human resource services in outpatient care includes various important aspects related to the interaction between patients and health workers, as well as the efficiency and effectiveness of the services provided. These aspects include communication and empathy skills from healthcare workers, which include skills in listening to patient complaints and providing easy-to-understand explanations regarding diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis (Sharkiya, 2023). Competence and professionalism are also key factors, including clinical knowledge, alertness in handling medical conditions, and compliance with ethical standards. In addition, the availability of adequate healthcare workers and easy access for patients are essential to ensure efficient services (Kwame & Petrucka, 2021). Coordination and collaboration between medical teams, both between doctors, nurses, nutritionists, and physiotherapists, are also needed to ensure integrated and sustainable services. Fast and efficient service processes, as well as the effective use of information technology, also improve patient comfort (Sharkiya, 2023). Respecting the rights and dignity of patients, including the privacy and confidentiality of information, as well as providing fair and non-discriminatory services, should not be ignored (Edgman-Levitan & Schoenbaum, 2021). Additionally, the ability to receive and act on patient feedback as well as an effective system for handling complaints and issues is essential for improving patient satisfaction. Ensuring the quality of human resource services in outpatient care is key to improving patient satisfaction, operational efficiency, and better health outcomes (Kwame & Petrucka, 2021).

A hospital's ability to provide healthcare services is measured by patient satisfaction levels, which include their entire experience from arrival to return. Patients expect the hospital to provide high-quality services when they come to consult about the health problems they are facing (Muhammad Al Rajab, 2023). Challenges in outpatient services include several important aspects. One of them is care coordination, where good coordination between various health care providers is needed to provide holistic care. In addition, time management becomes a big challenge, especially in busy clinics, where it is important to manage patient wait times so that they are not too long. The availability of resources is also a crucial factor, with the need to provide an adequate number of healthcare workers to handle large patient numbers. On the other hand, the role of technology is crucial in overcoming these challenges. Telemedicine, for example, allows remote consultations via video calls, which is especially helpful for patients living in remote areas. In addition, health information management systems can improve efficiency and accuracy in patient data storage and access, which in turn improves the quality of health services (Kwame & Petrucka, 2021).

The systematic literature review approach was chosen because it allows for the collection and analysis of data from various published studies, thus providing a thorough and evidence-based understanding of the topic being researched. This

approach helps in compiling a complete picture by integrating findings from various studies, resulting in stronger and more reliable conclusions.

To examine "Quality of Human Resource Services in Outpatient Care on Outpatient Satisfaction in Hospitals," the PICOS (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcomes, Study design) framework can be used to design clear and focused research questions, ensuring that the results of this study make a significant and applicable contribution in the context of human resource management.

Population: In this study, the population that will be the subject is outpatients in hospitals. This group includes a wide range of demographics of patients receiving health care in the outpatient unit.

Intervention: The intervention to be evaluated is the quality of human resource services in the outpatient unit. This includes aspects such as the competence of healthcare workers, empathy, communication, availability of healthcare workers, and the efficiency of services provided to patients.

Comparison: The comparison group in this study could include outpatients who received services before and after the implementation of the human resource service quality improvement program. This comparison will help assess the effectiveness of the interventions carried out.

Outcomes: The expected outcome of this intervention is an increase in outpatient satisfaction. Patient satisfaction indicators can include patient perception of service quality, satisfaction with communication and interaction with health workers, and overall satisfaction with the services received.

Study design: The research methods to be used include quantitative studies such as patient satisfaction surveys and statistical analysis to assess the relationship between service quality and patient satisfaction. Qualitative studies such as in-depth interviews with patients and healthcare workers can also be used to gain deeper insights into their experiences and perceptions.

Using the PICOS framework in this study helps to design a structured and systematic study. This ensures that every aspect of the research is carefully considered, and that the results obtained are relevant and reliable. This research is expected to provide valuable insights into how the quality of human resource services in outpatient units affects patient satisfaction, as well as provide recommendations for improving services in hospitals.

In designing a clear and focused research question in a systematic review with the topic "Quality of Human Resource Services in Outpatient Versus Outpatient Satisfaction in Hospitals," the PICOS framework was used to answer the important question: "How does the quality of human resource services in outpatient units affect outpatient satisfaction in hospitals?"

This study uses the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) approach to evaluate how the quality of human resource (HR) services in the outpatient unit affects patient satisfaction. The population studied was outpatients in hospitals with various

demographics. The interventions evaluated included the quality of HR services, including health worker competence, empathy, communication, health worker availability, and service efficiency. To assess the effectiveness of this intervention, comparisons were made between groups of patients who received services before and after the implementation of the HR quality improvement program.

The expected result is an increase in outpatient satisfaction, which is measured through the perception of service quality, satisfaction with communication and interaction with health workers, and overall satisfaction with the services received. The study used both quantitative and qualitative study designs, including patient satisfaction surveys and in-depth interviews. The literature search strategy includes the use of academic databases with relevant keywords, while the extracted data will include important information from each selected article. The results of these studies will be synthesized narratively and, where possible, through meta-analyses to provide in-depth insights into the relationship between HR service quality and outpatient satisfaction.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Quality of Service

Hospital service quality is defined as an institution's ability to consistently deliver effective, efficient, and compliant healthcare services that meet patient needs and satisfy service providers. These qualities involve various aspects that include interactions between patients and healthcare workers, the physical environment of the hospital, administrative processes, and patient health outcomes. Hospital service quality is defined as an institution's ability to consistently deliver effective, efficient, and compliant healthcare services that meet patient needs and satisfy service providers. These qualities involve various aspects that include interactions between patients and healthcare workers, the physical environment of the hospital, administrative processes, and patient health outcomes. (Darzi et al., 2023)

The results of the research from the journal "Service Quality in the Healthcare Sector" (Darzi et al., 2023) identify and classify various dimensions of health service quality based on existing literature. It found 41 dimensions that were grouped into four main categories: physical environment (servicescape), personnel, hospital administration, and patients. The aspect of the physical environment is very important in determining the quality of services. This includes the quality of the physical environment, the diagnostic aspects of care, resources and capacity, and financial and physical access to care. Research shows that a good physical environment, including the cleanliness and comfort of the facility, has a significant impact on patient satisfaction. The interaction between patients and health workers is a very influential dimension. Factors such as healthcare worker behavior, efficacy, efficiency, empathy, and quality of interaction are considered important by patients. The competence and ability of health workers to provide reliable and responsive services also greatly determines patient satisfaction. Administrative aspects include the patient admission process, guarantees,

healthcare delivery systems, and hospital management. Efficiency in good administrative and management processes has a direct impact on the patient experience and their satisfaction with the services provided.

The quality of outpatient care in hospitals can be evaluated using five main dimensions that often refer to the "SERVQUAL" model developed by Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry. The reliability dimension, which measures a hospital's ability to deliver promised services accurately and on time, ensures that patients receive consistent and reliable care. The responsiveness dimension reflects the willingness and ability of medical staff to respond quickly and appropriately to patient requests and complaints, so that the services provided become more efficient and satisfactory. The Assurance dimension involves the knowledge and courtesy of the staff as well as their ability to instill trust and confidence in patients, including competence and courtesy in providing a sense of security during treatment. Furthermore, the dimension of empathy indicates the individual's attention and understanding of the patient's needs, including the ability of the service provider to provide personal attention and care for each patient's unique condition. Finally, tangibles refer to the physical appearance of facilities, equipment, personnel, and communication materials, including the comfort and cleanliness of the facility and the professionalism of medical staff. These five dimensions are used to assess the overall quality of outpatient services, which can ultimately affect patient satisfaction and loyalty. The application of the SERVQUAL model helps hospitals in identifying areas that need improvement in their services to achieve better quality and improve patient satisfaction (Shi & B, 2020)

In the study (AlRyalat et al., 2019) emphasized that to achieve high patient satisfaction, hospitals must focus on improving the quality of interaction between patients and health workers (doctors and nurses) to be the main factor affecting patient satisfaction, reducing the waiting time needed for patients to complete various services in the outpatient clinic, from entering the clinic to completing the visit, is another important factor. Long wait times can reduce patient satisfaction, although the study found that the impact was smaller than other factors, keeping the facility clean is also an important indicator of service quality. Good hygiene not only reflects professionalism and attention to detail, but can also increase patient comfort and trust in the services provided, The quality of food service in cafeterias and beverage machines was also assessed in this study. While it may be seen as an additional factor, good food service can improve a patient's overall impression of a healthcare facility, and ensuring the availability of medicines in hospital pharmacies is another aspect of service quality that affects patient satisfaction. Patients who do not find the medication they need in the hospital may feel disappointed and this can affect their assessment of the overall quality of the service. By paying attention to and improving these factors, hospitals can improve patient satisfaction and their loyalty.

Human Resource Management in Hospitals

HR management in hospitals is a crucial aspect that affects the quality of health services and patient satisfaction. Through the implementation of effective management strategies, such as continuous training, performance evaluation, and employee empowerment, hospitals can improve operational efficiency and the quality of services provided. In the study "Assessment of human resources management practices in Lebanese hospitals", the main challenges faced in human resource management in hospitals include poor employee retention, lack of qualified personnel, and limitations in the performance evaluation system. Low employee retention is often due to a lack of job satisfaction and limited career development opportunities, especially among nurses who are the backbone of hospital operations. In addition, the shortage of qualified personnel exacerbates the situation as many hospitals struggle to find qualified candidates for essential positions such as healthcare workers and quality managers. Limitations in the performance evaluation system are also a major obstacle, because without an effective assessment mechanism, hospitals have difficulty in evaluating staff competencies and performance objectively and continuously. To address these challenges, several strategies have been implemented, including ongoing training and education for employees. Continuous training aims to improve the skills and knowledge of healthcare workers so that they can provide better services and feel more satisfied with their jobs. Additional education is also important to fill the shortage of qualified personnel, by providing opportunities for staff to acquire the necessary qualifications for higher positions or rare specialties. Through this approach, hospitals can improve employee retention, ensure the availability of a qualified workforce, and strengthen performance evaluation systems to support the improvement of overall healthcare quality. An effective performance evaluation system is essential to ensure that employees are working according to the expected standards. Limitations in this system can hinder the ability of hospitals to evaluate and improve staff competencies. (El-Jardali et al., 2009)

In the journal "Human Resource Management Practices in Government & Private Hospitals (An Empirical Study in Indian Context)" The study also highlights the importance of continuous training and education for employees as a key strategy to overcome challenges such as poor employee retention and shortage of qualified personnel (Rajak & Mishra, 2015). In addition, transformational leadership has a significant positive impact on employee empowerment and job satisfaction. Transformational leadership, which is characterized by inspiration, motivation, individualized attention, and intellectual stimulation, encourages employees to feel more empowered and engaged in their work. Employee empowerment, in turn, improves work performance and employee satisfaction. The study shows that when employees feel empowered and valued by their leaders, they tend to be more satisfied with their work, more motivated, and more productive. This study emphasizes the importance of transformational leadership styles in creating a positive and supportive

work environment, which can ultimately improve service quality and overall organizational performance (Choi et al., 2016).

Patient Satisfaction

According to Philip Kotler, customer satisfaction is defined as a person's "feeling of pleasure or disappointment" resulting from comparing the perceived performance of a product (or result) with their expectations (Kotler & Davis, 2015). In other words, customer satisfaction occurs when the service or product received meets or exceeds customer expectations, resulting in a feeling of pleasure. On the other hand, if the performance of a service or product does not meet expectations, customers will feel disappointed. This definition emphasizes the importance of perception and expectations in determining customer satisfaction levels. Perception of product or service performance is influenced by previous experience, recommendations from others, and promises made by service providers or sellers. Therefore, customer expectation management through clear communication and service consistency is key in achieving and maintaining customer satisfaction (Dudovskiy, 2021).

Customer satisfaction is an important concept in marketing management that is often measured systematically by companies to improve customer retention. According to Kotler, wise companies measure customer satisfaction regularly because highly satisfied customers tend to be more loyal, buy more products when the company introduces new products, talk both about the company and its products, pay less attention to competitor brands, and are more resistant to price changes (Kotler & Davis, 2015).

The relationship between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty is disproportionate. For example, if customer satisfaction is rated on a scale of 1 to 5, at a very low level of satisfaction (level 1), the customer is more likely to leave the company and even speak ill of it. At levels 2 to 4, customers are quite satisfied but still easy to switch to better offers. At level 5, customers are very likely to buy back and even spread good words about the company (Kotler & Davis, 2015).

Customer satisfaction measurement can be done through periodic surveys that track overall customer satisfaction directly and ask additional questions to measure repeat purchase intentions, likelihood or willingness to recommend companies and brands to others, as well as perceptions of certain attributes or benefits that are likely to be related to customer satisfaction (Kotler & Davis, 2015).

From the above literature sources, patient satisfaction in hospitals is an important aspect similar to customer satisfaction in business in general. Hospitals need to systematically measure how they serve patients, identify the factors that make up satisfaction, and transform operations and marketing based on those results. Patient satisfaction measurement is typically done through periodic surveys that track overall satisfaction and ask additional questions to gauge repeat visit intent, likelihood or willingness to recommend a hospital, as well as perceptions of certain attributes or benefits that may be associated with patient satisfaction. There is a strong association

between patient satisfaction and loyalty. Highly satisfied patients tend to be more loyal, speak well of hospitals, and pay less attention to competing hospitals. High loyalty can create an emotional bond with the hospital, not just a rational preference. For example, patients who are "very satisfied" are more likely to come back and recommend the hospital to others compared to patients who are only "satisfied". A patient's assessment of service performance depends on many factors, including the type of loyalty relationship the patient has with the hospital. Consumers often form a more positive perception of the services of hospitals they already like. The negative effects of not meeting patients' expectations are stronger than the positive effects of exceeding their expectations. Therefore, it is important for hospitals to meet or exceed patient expectations in order to achieve high satisfaction (Kotler & Davis, 2015).

Patient satisfaction can significantly affect a hospital's reputation, especially in the internet age where information spreads rapidly. Dissatisfied patients can spread negative reviews widely, which can damage the hospital's image. Conversely, hospitals that achieve high patient satisfaction ratings can use the information as a marketing tool to attract more patients. Patient satisfaction also depends heavily on the quality of services provided. Quality here is defined as the totality of service features and characteristics that are able to meet the needs that have been stated or implied by the patient. Hospitals that meet or exceed patient expectations are considered to provide high-quality services. Overall, to achieve high patient satisfaction, hospitals must focus on measuring and improving service quality, understanding and meeting patient expectations, and carefully managing patient perception and loyalty (Kotler & Davis, 2015).

METHODS

In conducting a systematic review of journals, there are several stages of methods that will be used to ensure that the process of data collection, analysis, and synthesis is carried out in a transparent, systematic, and replicable manner. This process follows the guidelines that have been established (Moher et al., 2009) through the PRISMA guidelines.

1. PRISMA's flowchart illustrates the process of information flow through various stages in a systematic review, from identification to study inclusion. The following is an explanation of the stages:
2. Identification:
 - a. of records identified through database searching: The number of records identified through database searching. This is the first step where researchers search for relevant literature using specific keywords in various scientific databases such as PubMed, Google Scholar, Web of Science.
 - b. of additional records identified through other sources. This can include articles from bibliographies of already found articles or articles recommended by experts.

3. Screening:
 - c. of records after duplicates removed: The number of records after duplicates are removed. Duplicate records that appear from various search sources are removed to avoid repetition.
 - d. of records screened: The number of records screened. At this stage, the researcher reads the title and abstract to determine the relevance of the note to the research question.
 - e. of records excluded: The number of records excluded. Records that are irrelevant to the inclusion and exclusion criteria are removed.
4. Eligibility:
 - f. of full-text articles assessed for eligibility. Articles that pass the screening stage are then read in full to ensure that they meet the inclusion criteria.
 - g. of full-text articles excluded, with reasons: The number of full-text articles that were issued, along with the reasons. Articles that do not meet the inclusion criteria at this stage are deleted, and the reasons are noted (for example, because there is no relevant data, inappropriate methods, etc.).
5. Included (Inklusi):
 - h. of studies included in qualitative synthesis. Studies that meet the inclusion criteria are incorporated into a qualitative analysis to identify themes and patterns.
 - i. of studies included in quantitative synthesis (meta-analysis): The number of studies included in quantitative synthesis (meta-analysis). If the data are sufficiently homogeneous and statistically combinable, they will be included in the meta-analysis.
6. PRISMA's flowcharts help provide a clear visualization of how studies are selected and filtered in a systematic review, ensuring transparency and clarity of the selection process.

To determine the inclusion criteria in the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) method in research on the quality of human resource services in outpatient care on patient satisfaction in hospitals, we must pay attention to several important aspects. First, the relevance of the topic is key, where the article must discuss the quality of human resource services in outpatient care and its impact on patient satisfaction in hospitals. Second, the publication period must be carefully considered; Articles published in the last 10 years (for example, from 2014 to 2024) will ensure relevant and up-to-date data and findings. The language of publication is also important, where the article must be written in United Kingdom or Indonesian Language to facilitate understanding and analysis.

Furthermore, the research methods used in the article must include quantitative, qualitative, or mixed methods, with empirical data analysis relevant to the topic. The type of publication must also be considered, where articles published in academic journals are indexed and through a peer-review process will ensure the quality and validity of research results. The population and sample in the study should also be relevant, i.e. the study conducted on hospital outpatients, includes data from hospitals of various sizes and geographical locations to provide a comprehensive picture.

On the other hand, exclusion criteria must also be clearly defined. Articles that are irrelevant to the topic, such as those that discuss the quality of health care in inpatient or other non-outpatient health units, will be excluded. Articles published before 2014 or after 2024 will also not be included. The language of publication that is not in United Kingdom or Indonesian Language is also a reason for exclusion. Research methods that are unclear or are only opinion or editorial without empirical data, as well as those that use irrelevant research methods such as animal studies or laboratories that are not related to human health services, will be excluded. Using these clear and detailed inclusion and exclusion criteria, we can filter relevant articles and ensure that research is based on the most appropriate and high-quality literature

Table : List of Systematic Journal of Literature Review

It	Publisher	Heading	Abstract	Link	Year
1	Ayele, W. M., Ewunetu, A., & Chanie, M. G. (2022)	Level of satisfaction and associated factors among patients attending outpatient departments of south Wollo health facilities, Ethiopia	Patient satisfaction is a key metric for determining how efficient healthcare is delivered. When patients visit health care facilities, they express a clear desire for high-quality services.....	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10021765/pdf/pgph.0000761.pdf	2021
2	Ren, W., Sun, L., Tarimo, C. S., Li, Q., & Wu, J. (2021)	The situation and influencing factors of outpatient satisfaction in large hospitals: Evidence from Henan province, China	The level of outpatient satisfaction plays a significant role in improving the quality and utilization of healthcare services. Patient satisfaction gives providers insights into various aspects of services including the effectiveness of care and level of empathy....	https://bmchealthservres.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12913-021-06520-2	2021

3	Zhou, X., He, Q., Li, Q., Kuang, J., Han, Y., & Chen, J. (2022)	Factors Associated with Outpatient Satisfaction in Provincial Tertiary Hospitals in Nanchang, China: A Structural Equation Modeling Approach This study aimed to explore the relationship between patient satisfaction and its related factors in provincial tertiary hospitals. Six hundred outpatients in three provincial tertiary hospitals in Nanchang, China, were randomly selected. Structural equation modeling was used to analyze the relationship of the factors associated with outpatient satisfaction.....	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9351663/pdf/ijerph-19-08226.pdf	2022
4	Chandra, S., Ward, P., & Mohammadnezhad, M. (2019)	Factors associated with patient satisfaction in outpatient department of Suva sub-divisional health center, Fiji, 2018: A mixed method study Improved patient satisfaction is associated with increased levels of adherence to treatment processes and recommended prevention, and improved health outcomes.....	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6614334/pdf/fpubh-07-00183.pdf	2019

5	Rahma, A. Z., Yanuar, T., Shah, R., Program, S., Master, M., Faculty, E., And, B., University, E., & Excel, J. (2023)	The Relationship Between Service Quality, Patient Satisfaction, Behavioral Intentions And Prices In Outpatient Healthcare In The Hospital Industry This was a mixed method cross-sectional study employing both quantitative and qualitative designs. A random sample of 410 participants attending the outpatient services completed the self-administered structured questionnaire. The questionnaire focused on socio-demographic features, waiting time, doctors' communication, and patient trust....	https://ejournal.seaninstitute.or.id/index.php/Ekonomi/article/view/1487	2023
6	Al-Rayalat, S.A., Ahmad, Wa., Abu-Abila, M., Abdul-Jawad, T., Ali-Salim, M., Ahmad, Y., Hamdan, A., Salim, L., & Al-Awdi, M. (2019)	Factors affecting patient's satisfaction in outpatient clinics in Jordan: cross-sectional study In this cross-sectional study, we surveyed patients visiting outpatient's clinics at Jordan University Hospital (JUH). We focused on aspects that are, according to previous studies, significantly affecting patient's satisfaction, these include interaction with all healthcare providing personnel, time needed to complete different services, general cleanliness, and food services.....	https://jhmhp.amegroups.org/article/view/4837/pdf	2019

7	Abalkhel, M., Al-Najr, H., & Abu Karim, N. (2023)	Patient Satisfaction Study in Outpatient Setting in Tertiary Academic Hospital Patient Satisfaction in Outpatient Clinics The survey found that total outpatient satisfaction was 76.69±25.17, and the higher satisfaction factor scores were hospital facilities, Attitude and corporation of pharmacy staffs, language and communication of the physician, and registration process.....	https://assets-eu.researchsquare.com/files/rs-2557301/v1/df23856d-5d74-4aa8-8764-7c265be6a5fa.pdf?c=1680933576	2023
8	Bhatt, L. D., Ghimire, S., & Khanal, K. (2024)	Patient satisfaction and their determinants in outpatient department of a tertiary public hospital in Nepal: a cross-sectional study These findings illuminate the intricate qualities of patient satisfaction within our healthcare context, offering actionable insights for enhancement and guiding the trajectory of future research endeavors.....	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10902242/pdf/41687_2024_Article_696.pdf	2024

9	Mesfin, D., & Gintamo, T. (2019)	Patient satisfaction and associated factors with services provided at outpatient departments The overall of patient satisfaction level with the health service provided at the outpatient departments of the primary hospitals was 66.5% (95% C.I. 60.8%-72.2%). waiting time (AOR 3.65), informing patients about cause of illness (AOR, 2.46) and waiting area cleanliness (AOR 2.33) were among the significant predictors of patients satisfaction.....	https://ijphs.iaescore.com/index.php/IJPHS/article/view/20375/13156	2019
10	Duc Thanh, N., My Anh, B. T., Siem, C. H., Quynh Anh, P., Tien, P. H., Thi Phuong Thanh, N., Huu Quang, C., Ha, V. T., & Thanh Hung, P. (2022)	Patient Satisfaction With Healthcare Service Quality and Its Associated Factors at One Polyclinic in Hanoi, Vietnam	The overall outpatient satisfaction was 53.5%. There were five factors (facilities, services provision results, information transparency and administrative procedures, accessibility, and interaction and communication of staff)	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9684178/pdf/ijph-67-1605055.pdf	2022

11	Khuwa, Z. K., Matlala, S. F., & Ntuli, T. S. (2022)	Outpatients' satisfaction with healthcare services received at a district hospital in Botswana	<p>..... Results: 65% (95% CI: 58-71%) were satisfied but unsatisfied with: doctor's politeness (66.9%; 95% CI: 60-73%), explaining (67.8%; 95% CI: 61-73%), privacy (65.6%; 95% CI: 59-72%), skills (67.4%; 95% CI: 61-73%), confidence (67.4% 95% CI: 61-73%), compassion (66.5%; 95% CI: 60-72%) and waiting time (49.2%; 95% CI: 42-57%). Department visited predicted satisfaction (p=0.002); those from the Eye clinic and Sexual Reproductive Health clinic were satisfied compared to others.....</p>	<p>https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10336639/pdf/GMJ5603-0215.pdf</p>	2022
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12	Sanad, A. S., Sayed, A., Thabet, M., Omar, N. Al, & Mousa, O. (2020)	Assessing Patients' Satisfaction with the Quality of Services at the Outpatient Clinics in Minia Maternal and Children University Hospital, Egypt	<p>..... Majority of studied patient satisfied with timing, nursing care, physician care, surrounding environment and overall satisfaction. Waiting time, nurses' directions, physician communication, and surrounding area were the factors which affect patient satisfaction in this study. Finally, it may be concluded that the requirement for constant improvement of the quality and care in the health care setting has.....</p>	<p>https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ola-Mousa/publication/344069774_Assessing_Patients'_Satisfaction_with_the_Quality_of_Services_at_the_Outpatient_Clinics_in_Minia_Maternal_and_Children_University_Hospital_Egypt/links/5f50a38aa6fdcc9879c44234/Assessing-Patients-Satisfaction-with-the-Quality-of-Services-at-the-Outpatient-Clinics-in-Minia-Maternal-and-Children-University-Hospital-Egypt.pdf</p>	2020
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13	Azam, P., Akhlaq, A., Niazi, M. M., & Nawaz, S. (2023)	Impact of Outpatient Quality Services on Patient Satisfaction Regression Analysis showed a positive impact on the availability of services; thus 1% increase in service will lead to a 0.484% change in patient satisfaction. A negative relationship was also witnessed with a 1% increase in waiting time patient satisfaction is down by 0.119%....	https://ojs.njhsciences.com/index.php/njhs/article/view/486	2023
14	Haryadi, C. (2023)	The Influence of Image and Service Quality on Patient Satisfaction That Has an Impact on Patient Loyaltyservice quality with positive value to patient satisfaction at Harapan Keluarga Hospital with a sample value of 0, 407, the quality of service is positively valued to patient loyalty at The Family Hope Hospital with a sample value of 0.315....	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331828124 The influence of hospital image and service quality on patients' satisfaction and loyalty	2023

15	Kidanemariam, G., Gebrekidan, H., Dagnazgi, E. A., & Asfaw, K. (2023)	Improving Patient Satisfaction and Associated Factors at Outpatient Department in General Hospitals of Central Zone, Tigray, Northern Ethiopia, June 2018-August 2019: Pre- and Postinterventional Study	In the preintervention period, the patient satisfaction was 54.2%; after providing intervention, the patient satisfaction was increased to 77% in postinterventional study. Respondents who paid for the medical service were 41% less likely satisfied than those who had gotten free services. Participants whose age of 18-27 years were 22% more likely satisfied than whose age were 58 and greater.	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10665098/pdf/BMRI2023-6685598.pdf	2023
16	Alfarizi, M., & Ngatindriatun. (2022)	Determinant factors of hospital service quality and patient satisfaction: Hospital logistics management approach	Optimizing hospital logistics elements in private hospital specialist patient care is a challenge that is not easy because it requires strategic planning and proper resource management.	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/362845727_Determinant_factors_of_hospital_service_quality_and_patient_satisfaction_Hospital_logistics_management_approach	2022

17	Abbasi-Moghaddam, M. A., Zarei, A., Bagherzadeh, R., Dargahi, Yes., & Farrokhi, P. (2019)	Evaluation of service quality from patients' viewpointThe results indicated that among eight dimensions of health service quality, the patients were more satisfied with physician consultation, services costs and admission process. The highest and lowest mean scores were related to physician consultation (Mean = 4.17), and waiting time (Mean = 2.64), in that order.....	https://bmchealthservres.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12913-019-3998-0	2019
18	Liu, Y., Zhang, F., Guan, C., Song, B., Zhang, H., Fu, M., Wang, F., Tang, C., Chen, H., Guo, Q., Fan, L., Hou, X., Wang, H., Wu, B., Shan, G., Zhang, H., Yu, F., Lou, X., Xie, H., ... Guo, S. (2023)	Patient satisfaction with humanistic nursing in Chinese secondary and tertiary public hospitals: a cross-sectional survey	Humanistic care pertains to the abilities, attitudes, and behaviors central to patient-centered care, contributing to patients' sense of safety and wellbeing. This study aimed to assess the satisfaction of patients with humanistic nursing care in Chinese secondary and tertiary public hospitals.	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10498541/pdf/fpubh-11-1163351.pdf	2023

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

How does the quality of human resource services in the outpatient unit affect the satisfaction of outpatients in the hospital?

Based on a collection of journals that have been selected, the quality of human resource services (HR) in the outpatient unit has a significant influence on patient satisfaction. First, good communication and empathy from medical staff play a crucial role in improving patient satisfaction, as demonstrated by (Ren et al., 2021) and (Chandra et al., 2019). Effective communication between doctors and patients and an empathetic attitude can increase patient trust and comfort. Second, long wait times can lower patient satisfaction levels, as found by (Mesfin & Gintamo, 2019) and (Azam et al., 2023). Therefore, efficiency in service and reduction of waiting times are essential to improve patient satisfaction.

Adequate facilities and a comfortable environment also play an important role in determining patient satisfaction, as discussed by (Duc Thanh et al., 2022) and (Sanad et al., 2020). Good facilities can improve the patient experience while in the outpatient unit. In addition, the skills and competencies of medical staff, including nurses and doctors, have a profound effect on patient satisfaction, as demonstrated by (Bhatt et al., 2024) and (Abaalkhayl et al., 2023). High technical skills and medical knowledge give patients confidence regarding the quality of care received.

Patient trust in the healthcare services provided is also an important factor influencing satisfaction, as highlighted by (Liu et al., 2023). Patient satisfaction increases when they feel that the care they receive is of high quality and reliable. In addition, patient interaction and involvement in the treatment process, as affirmed by (Rahma et al., 2023) and (Alfarizi & Ngatindriatun, 2022), is essential. Patients who feel involved in medical decisions and are given adequate explanations about their condition tend to be more satisfied with the services received.

Finally, humanistic aspects of service, such as genuine care and care, have a profound effect on patient satisfaction, as found by Liu et al. (2023). A humane approach helps create a more supportive and comfortable care environment for patients. Overall, factors such as effective communication, minimal wait times, adequate facilities, staff skills and competencies, trust in services, patient engagement, and a humanistic approach to service all contribute to improved patient satisfaction. Efforts to improve and optimize these factors can lead to a more positive treatment experience and improve patient satisfaction levels in hospitals.

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